

A Note on the Condensation of ω -Bromoacetophenone with 1-*o*-Aminophenyl-3-Phenylthiocarbamide.

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In the course of an investigation on the action of ω -bromoacetophenone upon 1-*o*-aminophenyl-3-arylthiocarbamides, Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 71) obtained certain well-defined condensation products which he formulated as (II). The course of the reaction was represented as follows :

The author considered such reactions as highly improbable. Because it has been shown by a large number of investigators that the bromine atom of ω -bromoacetophenone is *always* eliminated as hydrogen bromide in its condensation with a compound with the grouping $\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{NHR}$ the final product being the hydrobromide of a cyclic base, having sulphur in the ring. In the case of 1-*o*-aminophenyl-3-arylthiocarbamides Ghosh assumed a greater reactivity of the ketonic group without adducing any experimental evidence thereof. It was, therefore, thought necessary to repeat Ghosh's experiment and ascertain the real nature of the compound to which he assigned the constitution (II). In dilute acetic acid solution the condensation product was an uncrystallisable oil. In 95% acetic acid solution a crystalline product was obtained in a very poor yield which on being thrice crystallised from glacial acetic acid melted at 223° (decomp.). (Found: C, 51.1; H, 4.09; Br, 24.0. Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{ON}_2\text{SBr}$: C, 51.0; H, 3.72; Br, 22.8 per cent). Ghosh's compound melted at 230°

(decomp.). The properties and analysis, however, agreed with those of Ghosh and the two compounds are regarded as identical. That this compound is the hydrobromide of a weak base is demonstrated by the following facts:

- (i) An aqueous-acetone solution of the substance was acidic to Congo-red paper.
- (ii) The substance liberated carbon dioxide when triturated with cold sodium bicarbonate solution and was converted into a base, m. p. 164° , which crystallised from alcohol in long pointed light straw-yellow needles. (Found: N, 10.44; $C_{15}H_{12}ON_2S$ requires N, 10.41 per cent).
- (iii) The same hydrobromide was obtained when the reaction was allowed to proceed in alcoholic solution and the base, liberated by pyridine, melted at 164° .

These facts definitely prove that Ghosh's compound is the hydrobromide of a base melting at 164° , which may be given the constitution (III) or (IV).

(III)

(IV)

The reaction involves the elimination of aniline during the condensation and surprise was expressed by Ghosh that a compound of the type (I) should so easily eliminate aniline. In fact instances of such type of hydrolysis where the aniline group is attached to the ring by means of a single bond are hardly to be met with. If, on the other hand, the intermediate compound is supposed to have the structure (V), there is no difficulty whatsoever of an explanation, since the easy hydrolysability of the $:C=NR$ group is well known. Ghosh also made another interesting observation that when 1-*o*-aminophenyl-3-allylthiocarbamide is condensed with ω -bromoacetophenone the allyl group, unlike the phenyl group, is not eliminated as allylamine. This appears to be due to the different character of the phenyl and allyl group. In the former case the intermediate compound reacts as (VI) whereas in the latter case as (VII), the phenyl group having a definite negative character. In the condensation product, therefore,

